

FINANCIAL CONTROL IN THE UNITED STATES

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Abstract: Country Overview, Financial Regulatory Authorities, Policy, Laws and Regulations, First National Anti-Money Laundering Priorities. Federal Reserve System, Department of the Treasury.

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The sweeping credit crunch of 2008 triggered several high-profile financial failures and prompted widespread debate about how the U.S. government regulates financial markets. Beyond efforts to resolve an immediate liquidity crisis, policymakers are considering longer-term efforts to significantly reorganize the rules governing financial markets and the regulatory agencies charged with enforcing them. Treasury Secretary Henry M. Paulson has pushed for the implementation of a series of reforms he initially proposed in March 2008. Paulson’s plan would shut down one regulatory agency, the Office of Thrift Supervision (OTS), and merge two others, the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and the Commodities Futures Trading Commission (CFTC). Overall, many analysts interpreted the plan as a broad move to empower yet another regulator, the U.S. Federal Reserve. Other policymakers and analysts advocate different approaches. Many Democrats in Congress aim to repeal or revise the Gramm-Leach-Bliley Act of 1999, which discarded financial safeguards applied during the Great Depression and opened the way for banks and insurance companies to compete with brokerage houses in offering complex investment products. Others stress major operational reforms at the SEC. Still others insist that federal intervention in markets is a mistake and that investment houses and other financial institutions which took undue risks should be allowed to collapse. The Federal Reserve, commonly referred to as the Fed, is the central bank of the United States. The Fed is responsible for regulating the U.S. monetary system (i.e. how much money is printed, and how it is distributed), as well as monitoring the operations of holding companies, including traditional banks and banking groups. Broadly speaking, its mandate is to promote stable prices and economic growth.

The Federal Reserve exerts regulatory oversight in a few different ways:

- Board of Governors: The national component of the federal reserve system is run by a seven-person Board of Governors, commonly called the Federal

Reserve Board. This group is managed by a chairman (currently Ben S. Bernanke) and vice chairman (Donald L. Kohn). Its main responsibility is to guide monetary policy by coordinating with the Federal Open Markets Committee (FOMC) and regional reserve banks. Toward this end, the board organizes a wide range of research and analytical operations. The board is also charged with overseeing the U.S. government's system of payments; supervising the financial services industry, including approving bank presidents and setting requirements for the amount of cash banks must hold in reserve; and coordinating and overseeing the actions of regional reserve banks.

- **Federal Open Markets Committee:** The FOMC is the Fed's primary monetary policymaking body. It consists of twelve members, including the seven members of the Board of Governors, the president of the Federal Reserve Bank of New York, and the presidents of four other regional banks (who serve on a rotating basis). The FOMC typically meets eight times a year and is charged with assessing the economic and financial landscape and setting the "federal funds rate," the benchmark interest rate at which the Fed loans money to banks.
- **Reserve banks:** The federal reserve banking system encompasses twelve regional banks with twenty-five total branches. These banks are regional arms of the U.S. central bank that act as intermediaries between local banks and the U.S. reserve banking system. They store and distribute reserves, process checks and other forms of interbank payments, and generally supervise the operations of commercial banks in their region. Reserve banks have additional regulatory authority over the 38 percent of U.S. commercial banks (mainly larger banks, including all national banks) that are members of the Federal Reserve system. These banks are considered stockholders of their local reserve bank and thus are required to hold 3 percent of their total capital at that bank.

Amidst the financial crisis of 2008, the Fed sought to use policy statements and its control of interest rates to influence legislative policy and calm capital markets. Chairman Bernanke has also encouraged lawmakers to pass a plan aimed at stimulating liquidity in financial markets, and has supported moves by the U.S. Treasury to make money available to some failing U.S. financial institutions. The U.S. Department of the Treasury, originally created specifically to manage government revenues (whereas the Federal Reserve manages payments), has evolved to encompass several different duties. It recommends and influences fiscal policy; regulates U.S. imports and exports; collects all U.S. revenues, including taxes; and designs and mints all U.S. currency.

In terms of financial regulation, the Treasury Department functions primarily through the operations of two agencies it oversees, the Office of the Comptroller of the Currency and the Office of Thrift Supervision, which regulate banks and savings and loans:

- Office of the Comptroller of the Currency: The Office of the Comptroller of the Currency, or OCC, is the primary means through which the Treasury regulates U.S. banks. It is headed by the comptroller of the currency (currently John Dugan). The OCC is responsible for chartering all U.S. banks and, more broadly, for ensuring the stability of the banking system. According to the OCC's website, it attempts the latter task by monitoring: "a bank's loan and investment portfolios, funds management, capital, earnings, liquidity, sensitivity to market risk, and compliance with consumer banking laws." Its responsibilities thus overlap, to a degree, with those of the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation (FDIC), which must also monitor banks' capital reserves and sensitivity to risk. If a bank doesn't comply with OCC standards, the agency holds the authority to take a variety of actions. It can force the ouster of senior bank personnel, force the bank to change certain practices, issue fines or penalties, and ultimately issue orders for the bank to close its operations.

- Office of Thrift Supervision: The Office of Thrift Supervision (OTS) is tasked with supervising federally-chartered savings and loan associations, also known as "thrifts." (Thrifts generally specialize in managing large savings deposits and issuing mortgages, and are often mutually held, meaning that involved borrowers and lenders have the ability to guide the association's management and financial practices.) The OTS regulates the formation and management of thrifts. It is also responsible for regulating savings and loan holding companies-firms that buy up rights to all the loans held by various thrifts-which gives it purview over several major U.S. banks and financial firms.

Although the US has confronted the COVID-19 pandemic, financial uncertainty, political upheaval and social unrest at some stage in 2020-2021, the united states stays a worldwide chief in economic balance and virtual transformation. The American economic system shrunk through 3.5% in 2020, its worst overall performance on the grounds that World War II,¹ however a amazing healing has professionals predicting the most powerful financial increase on the grounds that 1984, or maybe 1951.² The economic system is forecasted to extend in 2021 and 2022 through 6.7% and three.7%,³ respectively, due in component to a speedy vaccination rollout, USD \$2.8 trillion in stimulus money, surging call for and a developing jobs market.

Meanwhile, the COVID-19 pandemic has elevated digitalization with inside the US, consisting of the adoption of synthetic intelligence solutions⁴ and virtual banking. The digitalization of enterprise operations has pushed a upward thrust in productivity,⁶ and President Joe Biden's proposed American Jobs Plan consists of a USD \$6.5 billion price range closer to revitalizing virtual infrastructure over the following 8 years.⁷ Although America has development to make in bridging the virtual divide and strengthening virtual skills, it nevertheless ranked #2 at the 2020 Digital Evolution Scorecard, evolved through Tufts University's Fletcher School and Mastercard.

Digitalization has now no longer come with out hurdles, however. High-profile cyberattacks just like the 2016 election hacking, December 2020 Solar Winds cybersecurity assault and May 2021 Colonial Pipeline ransomware assault have more and more centered American authority's corporations and groups and uncovered vulnerabilities in country wide cyber resilience. Despite this worrisome landscape, America stays robust overall, and the Biden management is spearheading a couple of efforts to similarly bolster cybersecurity.

Alongside cybersecurity, the US' 2021 virtual schedule seeks to intensify virtual inclusion, invigorate the virtual economic system and counter the growing affect of China. Key federal legislative projects deal with virtual identity, information privateness and the law of digital currencies. The Federal Reserve is making plans to launch a record in September 2021 addressing the possibilities and dangers in virtual payments, consisting of crypto assets, stable coins and a likely important financial institution virtual currency (CBDC).^{eight} Although the Federal Reserve has been clean that it has no on the spot plans to trouble a CBDC, Federal Reserve Chair Jerome Powell mentioned that a CBDC may want to assist to undermine the recognition of privately-issued virtual currencies like cryptocurrencies and stable coins.

State legislatures have in addition been keen to deal with information protection, in addition to allow the digitalization of offerings like notarization. Colorado and Virginia have joined California in enacting complete information privateness laws, and Massachusetts, New York, North Carolina and Pennsylvania have lively bills.

The Federal Reserve is the central banking system of the United States: The Consumer Financial Protection Bureau (CFPB) is the US government agency responsible for consumer protection in the financial sector. In terms of rulemaking and legislation, the CFPB "enforces and enforces the Federal Consumer Finance Act to ensure that all consumers have access to fair,

transparent and competitive markets for consumer financial products and services. will enforce.

"The Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation (FDIC) "insures deposits; audits and supervises financial institutions for their safety, soundness, and consumer protection; makes large and complex financial institutions resolvable; Manage management."

The Federal Trade Commission (FTC) protects consumers and businesses by preventing anticompetitive, deceptive and unfair business practices. The FTC enforces laws and provides advocacy and education.

The Financial Crimes Enforcement Network (FinCEN) is an agency of the US Treasury Department. Its mission is to "protect the financial system from illicit use, combat money laundering and related crimes, including terrorism, and promote national security through the strategic use of financial authorities and the collection, analysis and dissemination of financial information.

The Financial Industry Regulatory Authority (FINRA) is a federally chartered non-profit organization that oversees broker-dealers in the United States as a self-regulatory organization.

The National Credit Union Association (NCUA) is an independent organization that issues charters and acts as the regulatory body for all federal credit unions. We also insure deposits with federal insurance credit unions.

The Office of the Comptroller of the Currency (OCC) is an independent department of the US Treasury Department. The OCC establishes bylaws and acts as the regulatory authority for all national banks and federal thrift houses. In addition, she oversees federal branches and agents of foreign banks.

The Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) is an independent federal agency that seeks to prevent market manipulation.

36-Hour Rule for Reporting Computer Security Incidents, November 2021: In November 2021, the Federal Reserve Board, the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation (FDIC), and the Office of the Comptroller of the Currency (OCC) published a final rule requiring "banking organizations" under their respective jurisdiction to notify their primary federal regulator within 36 hours in the event of certain types of computer-security incidents. The Rule separately requires "bank service providers" to "notify banking organization customers as soon as possible in the event of any incident that has or is reasonably likely to materially affect those customers for four or more hours". Bank service providers include any bank service company or other person that provides services subject to the Bank Service Company Act. The regulation takes effect

April 1, 2022, while banking organizations and their bank service providers must be in compliance by May 1, 2022.

Federal Trade Commission's Update to Safeguards Rule, October 2021: In October 2021, the Federal Trade Commission published an update to the "Safeguards Rule" under the Gramm-Leach-Bliley Act. Learn how non-bank financial institutions subject to the FTC can protect their customers' financial information. Banks, bank holding companies, and their subsidiaries are subject to separate guidelines and standards issued by federal banking regulators, including the OCC, Fed, and FDIC. The update applies to institutions "engaged in financial activities," such as auto dealers, real estate appraisers, accountants, investment advisors, and universities participating in federal financial assistance programs. In addition to being covered by existing rules, the amended safeguard rules may apply to Internet service providers, the gig economy, and online marketplaces.

Updated rules now require multi-factor authentication (MFA) when employees, customers, or other individuals access information systems. The FTC imposed a serious violation fine of \$43,792 per day per violation.

This revised rule came into effect on January 10, 2022. However, important provisions, including MFA requirements, will come into effect and be enforced on December 9, 2022.

RFI on the Use of Biometric Technology in the Public and Private Sectors, 8 October 2021: The Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) has issued a Request for Information (RFI) on the use of biometric technology in the public and private sectors. The notice states: Areas where these technologies are used. the sites they use; the current principles, practices or policies governing their use; 11 The comment period ends on January 15, 2022.

The Federal Financial Institutions Examination Council (FFIEC) issued its steering on Authentication and Access to Financial Institution Services and Systems, which info authentication and get right of entry to threat control ideas and practices for virtual banking offerings and statistics structures. The steering addresses the subsequent ideas and practices:

“Conducting a threat evaluation for get right of entry to and authentication to virtual banking and statistics structures”

Identifying all customers and clients for which authentication and get right of entry to controls are needed, and figuring out the ones customers and clients who may also warrant stronger authentication controls, inclusive of MFA.

Periodically comparing the effectiveness of person and patron authentication controls. Implementing layered safety to shield towards unauthorized get right of entry to monitoring, logging, and reporting of sports to discover and music unauthorized get right of entry to identifying dangers from, and imposing mitigating controls for, e mail structures, Internet get right of entry to, patron name centers, and inner IT assist desks.

Identifying dangers from, and imposing mitigating controls for, a patron-permitted entity's get right of entry to a monetary institution's statistics structures. Maintaining cognizance and training applications on authentication dangers for customers and clients.

Verifying the identification of customers and clients": The Financial Crimes Enforcement Network (FinCEN) has issued the first national priorities to combat money laundering and terrorist financing under the requirements of the Money Laundering Act 2020 (AMLA). Priorities developed in consultation with federal and state banking regulators, law enforcement and national security agencies, Treasury Departments and Attorneys General include:

- Corruption
- Cybercrime, including related cybersecurity and cryptocurrency considerations
- Domestic and foreign terrorist financing
- Scam
- Cross-border criminal organization activities
- Drug trafficking activities
- Human trafficking and smuggling
- Diffusion finance

Regarding cybercrime, FinCEN said: As a love scam and identity theft. FinCEN updates the priorities every four years to reflect the evolving threat landscape and publishes a rule detailing how financial institutions integrate the priorities into their AML programs. According to AMLA.

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